

Polarizability of ferrocene derivatives using new empirical approach

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The polarizabilities of some ferrocene derivatives have been calculated using a new empirical approach based on the square of the sum of the atomic hybrid components (τ_A) as given by the relation $\alpha(\text{ahc}) = 4/N[\sum_A \tau_A]^2 (\text{\AA}^3)$, where the summation proceeds over all atoms $A = 1, 2, 3 \dots$, and N is the total number of electrons in the molecule. Scales have been presented, where the derivatives are classified in order of their polarization properties. Common trends and patterns of behaviour are recognized and discussed.

Miller and Savchik¹ proposed a new empirical approach to the calculation of the average molecular polarizability by taking it as a square of the sum of atomic hybrid components. In this work, we have applied the method for the determination of polarizabilities of ferrocene and its derivatives and compared the results with those obtained by Semwal and Balodi² using Lippincott and Stutman's³ method. These compounds contain aromatic cyclopentadienyl rings interacting with an Fe atom through their π -electron systems. These rings are staggered (D_{5d}) and eclipsed (D'_{5h}) and difference in the electronic structure between the two forms is very small. These systems are of potential interest because they contain transition metals which may offer new properties due to the presence of low lying excited states in many cases. Organometallics have recently attracted the interest of those who search for novel and efficient non-linear optical materials⁴⁻⁷. Moreover the delocalized π -electron of the aromatic moieties in these systems have been shown to be instrumental in the formations of large hyperpolarizabilities. The functional form of the method used in this work is represented by the equation,

$$\alpha(\text{ahc}) = \frac{4}{N} [\sum_A \tau_A]^2 (\text{\AA}^3) \quad (1)$$

where N represents the number of electrons in the molecule and ahc stands for atomic hybrid components τ_A of α for each atom in a particular hybrid configuration. The summation proceeds over all atoms A in the molecule; τ_A depends on the type of bonding through the hybridization of atomic orbitals on A . For each atom A , one value of τ_A is used for each type of hybridization and the number of and type of bonds as well as, lone pairs are incorporated into the hybrid state of each atom^{1,8}.

The purpose of this work is to (i) explain a new empirical approach for the calculation of average molecular polarizability, (ii) to demonstrate that the concept of atomic hybrid states can be used in the formulation of a set of parameters, τ_A , to calculate molecular polarizability, and (iii) to obtain a set of atomic polarizability of α_A values for different hybrid states.

Rationalization of the empirical approach :

The functional form of the empirical formula proposed in this investigation can be rationalized with the variational-perturbation approach⁹ proposed by Hylleraas¹⁰ and Hasse¹¹. The xx component of molecular polarizability is expressed in the form :

$$\alpha_{xx} = \frac{4}{\alpha_0} \left[\overline{(x_1 - \bar{x})^2} - (N-1) \overline{(x_1 - \bar{x})(x_2 - \bar{x})} \right] \quad (2)$$

where N is the no. of electrons, \bar{x} is the average position of an electron in the x -direction, $\overline{(x_1 - \bar{x})^2}$ is the mean square deviation of an electron from its average position, and $\overline{(x_1 - \bar{x})(x_2 - \bar{x})}$ is the average correlation between two electrons in the x -direction. The average value of the operator q ,

$$\bar{q} = \int \Psi^* q \Psi d\tau \quad (3)$$

is calculated with the zeroth-order wave function Ψ obtained from perturbation theory. If the term in brackets in eq. (2) is rewritten to include a summation over all electrons $i, j = 1, 2, 3 \dots N$, then

$$\alpha_{xx} = \frac{4}{N\alpha_0} \left| \sum_{ij} \overline{(x_i - \bar{x}_i)(x_j - \bar{x}_j)} \right|^2 \quad (4)$$

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$$= \frac{4}{Na_0} [L_{xx}]^2 \quad (5)$$

The term in brackets in eqs. (4) and (5) reduces to

$$L_{xx} = [\sum_{ij} \overline{(x_i x_j)} - (\sum_i \overline{x_i})^2] \quad (6)$$

for closed-shell systems, the zeroth-order wave function may be approximated by an antisymmetrized product of molecular orbitals, Ψ_μ , $\mu = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, and spin function η and $\bar{\eta}$ with z components equal to $\pm 1/2$:

$$\Psi = (N!)^{-1/2} A \{ \Psi_1(1)\eta(1)\Psi_1(2)\bar{\eta}(2)\dots \} \quad (7)$$

substituting eq. (7) into eq. (6) yields

$$L_{xx} = -2 \sum_{\mu} \sum_{\nu} \int \Psi_{\mu}^* \chi_{\nu} \Psi_{\nu} d\tau \int \Psi_{\nu}^* \chi_{\mu} \Psi_{\mu} d\tau + 2 \sum_{\mu} \int \Psi_{\mu}^* \chi^2 \Psi_{\mu} d\tau \quad (8)$$

where μ and ν refer to the occupied molecular orbitals. The molecular orbitals are expanded as a linear combination of atomic orbitals χ_{At} :

$$\Psi_{\mu} = \sum_A \sum_t C_{At\mu} \chi_{At} \quad (9)$$

where t may refer S , P_x , P_y and P_z atomic orbitals or to hybrid atomic orbitals on atoms $A = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ substituting eq. (9) into eq. (8) and using the zero differential overlap approximation yields,

$$L_{xx} = \sum \sqrt{a_0} \tau_{Axx} \quad (10)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{a_0} \tau_{Axx} = & -2 \sum_B \sum_{t,u} \sum_{v,w} \sum_{\mu,\nu} C_{At\nu}^* C_{Au\nu} C_{Bv\nu}^* C_{Bw\mu} \\ & \times \int \chi_{At}^* x \chi_{Au} d\tau \int \chi_{Bv}^* x \chi_{Bw} d\tau + 2 \sum_t \sum_u \sum_v \sum_{\mu} C_{At\mu}^* C_{Au\mu} \\ & \times \int \chi_{At}^* x^2 \chi_{Au} d\tau \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

provides the link between the proposed empirical formula, eq. (1) and a molecular orbital model. Atomic orbitals t , u , v , and w are centered on atoms A and B in At , Au , Bv and Bw . It is convenient to assume that Ψ_{μ} , $\mu = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, are the localized molecular orbitals studied extensively by England *et al.*^{12,13}, their orbitals, confined to the region of a chemical bond, are written as a sum of hybrid atomic or π -orbitals. For acyclic hydrocarbons two center localized molecular orbitals are found, whereas for condensed hydrocarbons two- to four center localized molecular orbitals connected through a set of adjacent atoms are obtained.

To complete the rationalization of eq. (1), the components of polarizability α_{xx} obtained with eq. (2) and similarly α_{yy} and α_{zz} , are assumed to be calculated with the

XYZ coordinate system oriented along the principal axes of the polarization ellipsoid. Then the average molecular polarizability,

$$\alpha_M = 1/3 [\alpha_{xx} + \alpha_{yy} + \alpha_{zz}]$$

is obtained from,

$$\alpha = \frac{4}{N} [\sum_A \tau_A]^2 \quad (12)$$

Results and discussion

The calculated values of average molecular polarizabilities of 20 ferrocenes are given in Table 1 along with the values obtained by Semwal and Balodi² using Lippincott and Stutman's³ method. The empirical approach proposed with $\alpha(\text{ahc}) = 4/N [\sum_A \tau_A]^2$ (\AA^3) resulted from an attempt to obtain molecular polarizabilities for atoms in various hybrid states. The empirical approach proposed in this investigation appears to have several advantages over other methods like, (i) fewer parameters are required, (ii) τ_A does not depend on atoms to which atom A is bonded, but rather bonding is contained implicitly in the choice of atomic hy-

Table 1. Molecular polarizabilities of ferrocene and some derivatives (10^{-25} cm^3)

Sl. no.	Compd.	α_M	
		Lippincott and Stutman's method	Miller's method
1.	(C ₅ H ₅) ₂ Fe	200.244	190.41
2.	Fer-NH ₂	205.68	201.87
3.	Fer-CHO	211.567	205.897
4.	Fer-CN	211.71	208.75
5.	Fer-CH ₃	211.85	209.39
6.	Fer-Cl	214.982	208.60
7.	Fer-CC≡H	217.317	214.473
8.	Fer-CH=CH ₂	220.99	219.897
9.	CHO-Fer-CHO	223.59	225.763
10.	Fer-C-CH ₃	223.75	225.900
11.	Fer-CH ₂ Cl	226.382	227.92
12.	Fer-I	233.501	237.712
13.	Fer-CHCl ₂	240.755	247.737
14.	Fer-CH ₂ I	244.30	255.668
15.	Fer-CHI ₂	276.57	304.921
16.	Fer-CH=CH-Ar	345.687	305.496
17.	CHO-Fer-CH=CH-Ar	407.45	333.097
18.	Ar-CH=CH-Fer-CH=CH-Ar	488.45	396.468
19.	Fer-CH=CH-Ar-NO ₂	346.849	458.218
20.	Fer-H=CH-Ar-CH=CH-Fer	571.62	528.878

brid component τ_A and (iii) only one component τ_A is needed for each atomic hybrid configuration. For each atom A, one value of τ_A is needed for each type of bond as well as lone pairs are automatically incorporated into a parameter τ_A by the hybrid state of each atom. In the determination of τ_A , for example, from the average polarizability of H_2 , one obtains $(\alpha_H/8)^2 = \tau_H = 0.314 \text{ \AA}^{3/2}$ and then from α_{CH_4} , $\tau_C = |\sqrt{10/4}\alpha_{CH_4} - 4\tau_H| = 1.294 \text{ \AA}^{3/2}$, for carbon in the tetrahedral hybrid configuration τ_C (te te te te). Then ethylene ($\tau_C = 1.436 \text{ \AA}^{3/2}$) and benzene ($\tau_C = 1.428 \text{ \AA}^{3/2}$) for the hybrid state C (tr tr tr π), finally acetylene yields $\tau_C = 1.393 \text{ \AA}^{3/2}$ for C (di di $\pi\pi$). Using the same method we have determined the value of $\tau_{Fe} = 3.917 \text{ \AA}^{3/2}$.

The α_M value for ferrocene is $189.7 \times 10^{-25} \text{ cm}^3$ where as our theoretical value of α_m is $190.41 \times 10^{-25} \text{ cm}^3$ a close agreement. The small difference may be caused due to several reasons of the mechanism of its structural interpretations i.e. the complex mechanisms of distribution of the nine valence electron pairs of ferrocene among 10 (Fe-C) and 10 (C-C) bonds. The (Fe-C) bonds show very small ionic character and treating the molecule on the basis of electroneutrality principle, there are many compatible structures. The order of polarizability of different substituents in ferrocene derivatives is found to be as follows: $NH_2 < CHO < Cl < CN < CH_3 < -C\equiv CH < CH=CH_2 < -CoCH_3 < CH_2Cl < CHCl_2 < CH_2I < CHI_2$.

The trend specified above is a consequence of the important role of the delocalized π -electrons, which is common in these substrates. The main contributions connected with the iron atom and the interacting associated with it are considerably smaller. In the case of the ferrocenes, π -electrons delocalization through the ferrocene unit is not as effective as we observe a linear conjugated structure. For most of the molecules, our calculated values are in reasonable agreement with the experimental values. This indicates the wide applicability of the Miller's method to complicated

molecular systems and complex metal carbonyls.

Conclusions : The work reported here provides the following important conclusions : (i) organometallic systems in general offer additional structural flexibility to design non-linear molecular materials, (ii) they offer a rich variety of excited states to investigate the relative contributions of these states to optical non-linearity, (iii) in case of structures involving ferrocene, π -electron delocalization through the ferrocene unit is not as effective as in linear conjugated structures, and (iv) the $d-d$ transition of the metal does not make significant contribution to optical non-linearity compared to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions.

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